

Transport Sector Energy Demand Analysis Using MAED: The Case of Urban centers in Kenya.

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Executive Summary:

This report applies the MAED framework to analyse urban passenger transport energy demand in Kenya, using KNBS data for 2019, 2020, and 2025. The analysis focuses on population-driven passenger activity, load factors, modal split, and energy intensity. Two objectives are examined: reduction of energy demand in the transport sector and development of mass transit systems to address congestion. Results show that improving load factors and shifting energy use towards efficient public transport modes reduces energy demand per passenger-kilometre while supporting inclusive socio-economic development and reducing congestion in Kenyan urban centres.

Introduction:

Three cities in Kenya-Nairobi, Kisumu and Mombasa account for the greatest urban population (UN-Habitat country report,2023). As of 2019 the Kenya population was 47.6M of which 14M were in the urban centres (KNBS,2019). According to IEA transport sector consumers about 20% of energy demand. According to Strathmore University Repository (2019), Nairobi had over 300,000 registered vehicles contributing to urban congestion. Traffic counts on key access roads indicate upwards of 87,000 vehicles daily on major routes (Strategic Journals, 2023). Parking

capacity in the Nairobi CBD is limited to approximately 9,000 slots, intensifying competition and delays (Course Hero, 2023).

Urban centres in Kenya are experiencing sustained population growth, leading to rising passenger transport demand. Urban passenger transport underpins access to employment, education, and services, but increasing reliance on low-occupancy modes has contributed to congestion and high energy use. This report focuses exclusively on modelling of urban passenger transport using MAED.

Methodology:

The MAED model was applied to estimate urban passenger transport energy demand using population-driven transport activity variables. The model was first calibrated to a base year of 2019, an error of 0.005% was achieved between the calculated energy demand and energy demand from the modal. Table 1: below shows the equation that were used to generate the inputs for the modal and linear equation to achieve a reducing number of the modal split over project period for the different scenarios. An assumption was made for BAU, where the modal split was held constant from the base year-2019 to 2040.

Table 1: Table of Equation.

No.	Description	Equations
1.	Useful energy demand	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Average daily distance travelled per person, km</p> $PKU = DU \times 365 \times \frac{POLC}{1000}$ <p>Activity, 10⁹ p-km</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Population living in cities with public transport</p> </div> </div>

2.	Activity by mode	<p style="text-align: center;">Total Activity, 10⁹ p-km</p> $PKUTM(j) = PKU \times SUMT(j)$ <p style="text-align: center;">Activity by mode j, 10⁹ p-km</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Share of transport mode j</p>
3.	Energy Intensity	<p style="text-align: center;">Energy intensity mode j, kWh/100km</p> $UTMEI(j) = \frac{EIUTM(j)}{100 \times LFUTM(j)}$ <p style="text-align: center;">Energy intensity mode j, energy unit/p-km</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Load factor mode j</p>
4.	Final energy demand	<p style="text-align: center;">Activity mode j, 10⁹ p-km</p> $ECUTM(j) = PKUTM(j) \times UTMEI(j)$ <p style="text-align: center;">Final energy demand mode j, energy units</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Energy intensity mode j, energy units/p-km</p>
5.	Urban Activity	$Urban Activity_{p-km} = \sum_i Number(i) \times Milage_{km}(x) \times Load(i)_{Pass/vehicle}$
6.	Modal split	$Modal Split(i) = \frac{Number(i) \times Milage(i) \times Load(i)}{\sum_i Number(i) \times Milage(i) \times Load(i)}$
7.	Distance traveled per day	$Distance\ travelled\ per\ day_{km} = \frac{P-km\ urban\ activity}{Population\ in\ Large\ Cities \times 365}$

(Kiley,2026).

In the base year, Kenya’s total population was 47.6 million, of which 14.7 million resided in urban centres as indicated 2019 housing and population census (KNBS,2019). The urban population was assumed to increase by 31% between 2019 and 2040, while overall population growth was set at an annual rate of 1.9%. Average travel demand was defined using a per-capita daily travel distance of 15.6 km.

Modal type of Transport, Load factor, modal split and energy intensities were specified for each transport mode as shown in Table:1. These parameters were applied consistently across scenarios, while modal shares in projection years were adjusted linearly to reflect gradual changes in mobility patterns. The number of Motor vehicle used in the modal development were from KNBS economic report of 2019, 2022, 2025 and report of in-service vehicles by Ogot et al (2018).

Urban population was used as the primary driver of passenger transport demand. Passenger activity was expressed in urban passenger-kilometres, derived from population levels and assumed travel behaviour. Urban passenger-kilometre was allocated across transport modes using modal split and adjusted by mode-specific load factors. Final energy demand was then calculated using energy intensity coefficients and fuel split variables, enabling disaggregation of energy demand by transport mode and fuel type.

Table 2: Transport Modal input parameter tables

Mode of Transport	Load Factor	Modal Split	Energy Intensity
Car-diesel	2	2.97	228.31
Car-gasoline	2	8.57	213.62
Train-diesel	800	0.45	3004.03
Motorbike gasoline	2	45.19	40.29
Bus diesel	30	42.83	316.42

Results:

Figure 1: BAU Useful Activity

Figure 1 show that when we maintain business as usual, we will have an increase in energy demand and higher congestions in the urban centres particularly increase of Motorbikes shares of 57.7 Bpkm, followed by 54.7 Bpkm car gasoline 10.9Bpkm, car diesel 3.7Bpkm and finally train-diesel 0.6Bpkm.

Figure 2: Useful activity with Motorbikes included

Figure 2 show that passenger transport inclusion of motorbikes are included in the public transport, we will have an increase in useful activity in the urban centres with particularly increase of Motorbikes shares of 58

Bpkm, followed by 56.3 Bpkm for diesel buses, diesel train 13.2Bpkm, gasoline cars 0.5Bpkm and finally diesel cars 0.1Bpkm.

Figure 3: Useful Activity without Motorbike

Figure 3 shows passenger transport with the exclusion of motorbike, the results showed an increase in useful activity in the urban centres. That is diesel train to 73 Bpkm and diesel Buses to 54.9 Bpkm by projection year of 2040.

Figure 4: Total Useful activity for Urban Transport

Figure 4 shows Total useful passenger transport activity over the projection period. Urban passenger-kilometres increase from 84B pkm in the base year to 127 B pkm in 2040, corresponding to a 33.85% growth. The increase is attributed to populational increase in the urban centre using transport i.e from 14.7 million to 22.43 million passengers.

Final energy demand in the base year is estimated at 21.99 TWh. Scenario results show that changes in population and modal structure significantly influence future energy demand. Under the Business-as-Usual (BAU) scenario, final energy demand increases by 34%, reaching 33.4 TWh in 2040, reflecting unchanged energy splits and increasing congestion pressures.

In the public transport scenario including motorbikes, final energy demand decreases by 14% relative to the base year, resulting in an energy demand of 18.9 TWh, indicating moderate improvements in modal efficiency. The largest reduction is observed in the public transport scenario excluding motorbikes, where final energy demand decreases by 61.6%, reaching 8.54 TWh by 2040, due to higher load factors, improved modal efficiency, and reduced reliance on low-occupancy modes.

Figure 5: Energy demand Business as Usual

Figure 5 shows energy demand for business as usual over the projection period. Energy demand for the various modes of transport increase over the projection period. Firstly, Motorbike and gasoline cars demand are at 11.6 TWh, secondly diesel buses at 5.76 TWh thirdly diesel cars at 4.3 TWh and fourthly diesel train at 0.02 TWh.

Figure 6: Energy demand With Motorbike as Public

Figure 6 shows energy demand passenger transport with inclusion of Motorbikes over the projection period. Energy demand for the various modes of transport decrease over the projection period. Firstly, Motorbikes demand are at 11.6 TWh, secondly diesel buses at 5.9 TWh, thirdly gasoline cars at 0.5TWh and fourthly diesel trains at 0.4 TWh and finally diesel cars at 0.2 TWh .

Figure 7: Energy Demand Without Motorbikes

Figure 7 shows energy demand passenger transport with exclusion of Motorbikes over the projection period. Energy demand for the various modes of transport decrease over the projection period. Firstly, diesel

buses demand are at 5.7 TWh and secondly diesel train at 2.7 TWh. The rest presented zero energy demand.

Figure 8: Total energy demand per scenario

Figure 8 shows total energy demand over the projection period for all the scenarios developed in the model. As shown BAU increase by 34% from the base year reflecting 33.4 TWh, Public transport with inclusion of Motorbikes shows a decrease of 14% indicating 18.9 TWh by 2040 and finally public transport with exclusion of motorbike shows a decrease of 61% reflecting 8.5 TWh.

Discussion

The results demonstrate that future urban passenger transport energy demand in Kenya is strongly influenced by modal structure and congestion dynamics, rather than growth in useful activity alone. While total urban passenger transport activity increases by 33.85% between the base year and 2040, the associated energy demand varies significantly across scenarios depending on the dominance of low- or high-occupancy transport modes.

Under the Business-as-Usual (BAU) scenario, the growth in useful activity is largely absorbed by motorbikes and private cars, with motorbikes emerging as the dominant mode in urban passenger-

kilometres. This modal structure leads to rising congestion and low average load factors, resulting in a 34% increase in final energy demand by 2040. Despite their relatively low energy intensity per vehicle, the high share and low occupancy of motorbikes significantly contribute to increased energy demand and inefficient use of urban transport infrastructure.

When motorbikes are included within the public transport framework, useful activity continues to grow, but a gradual shift toward buses and rail is observed, accompanied by a decline in private car use. This results in moderate improvements in system efficiency and a 14% reduction in final energy demand relative to the base year. However, the continued dominance of motorbikes limits the potential energy savings, indicating that partial modal shifts alone are insufficient to fully decouple activity growth from energy demand.

The exclusion of motorbikes from public transport, combined with a strong expansion of high-capacity modes, produces the most substantial efficiency gains. In this scenario, useful activity is primarily absorbed by buses and rail, leading to reduced congestion, and high useful activity in the diesel train and diesel buses. As a result, final energy demand decreases by 61.6% by 2040, despite continued growth in total passenger activity. This outcome highlights the critical role of mode consolidation and capacity utilisation in reducing transport energy demand in rapidly urbanising contexts.

Overall, the findings confirm that managing modal shares and congestion is essential for achieving sustainable urban transport outcomes. Without targeted policy intervention, growth in urban mobility leads to disproportionate increases in energy demand. Conversely, a strategic shift toward efficient, high-capacity public transport modes enable substantial energy demand reductions while accommodating rising passenger transport activity, consistent with long-term urban sustainability objectives.

According to Guo et al., (2020) motor cycle ban policy was implemented in China, though there are other social economic effects. scenario three of reducing the number of motorbikes is possible in Kenya when policies

are put in place, furthermore the government to increase the number of public transports means like introducing the Trams for in city movement and diesel train for out city.

Barrier encountered in implementation are, firstly related to social economic where reduced house hold income may be evidence in Motor cycle industry y leading to high resistance of the suggested scenario. Secondly, we have the government looking the reduction of GDP in the transport sector.

Conclusion:

This study applied the MAED model to assess future urban passenger transport energy demand in Kenya under alternative mobility scenarios to 2040. The results confirm that while urban passenger transport activity is projected to grow by 33.85%, driven by population growth and increasing mobility needs, energy demand outcomes depend strongly on modal structure and congestion levels, rather than activity growth alone. Under the Business-as-Usual scenario, rising reliance on motorbikes and private cars leads to increased congestion and low load factors, resulting in a 34% increase in final energy demand by 2040. This demonstrates that maintaining current mobility trends will significantly intensify energy consumption and urban transport inefficiencies.

Introducing public transport while retaining motorbikes yields moderate energy savings, with a 14% reduction in final energy demand, but the persistence of low-occupancy modes limits the overall efficiency gains. In contrast, a strong modal shift toward high-capacity public transport modes, accompanied by the exclusion of motorbikes from core public transport services, produces the most favourable outcome. Despite continued growth in passenger activity, final energy demand decreases by 61.6%, reflecting higher load factors, reduced congestion, and improved energy efficiency per passenger-kilometre.

The key lesson from this analysis is that effective management of modal shares and capacity utilisation is essential for decoupling urban mobility growth from energy demand. Partial interventions yield limited benefits, whereas comprehensive policies that prioritise efficient public transport systems can simultaneously address energy demand reduction,

congestion mitigation, and sustainable urban mobility objectives. These findings provide a strong analytical basis for transport and energy policy decisions aligned with Kenya Vision 2030 and long-term sustainable development goals.

Policies suggested

The results underline the importance of modal shift policies in shaping future urban transport energy demand in Kenya. Scenarios favouring high-capacity public transport modes demonstrate that significant reductions in energy demand can be achieved even as passenger transport activity continues to grow. Policies that prioritise bus rapid transit and urban rail expansion, regulate the role of motorbikes in dense urban corridors, and discourage low-occupancy private vehicle use are therefore critical for managing congestion and improving energy efficiency. Integrating these measures with urban land-use planning and demand management strategies would further enhance system performance. These findings directly support Kenya Vision 2030 objectives by promoting efficient infrastructure development, reducing fuel consumption and import dependency, improving urban mobility, and advancing environmentally sustainable transport systems.

Reference

Course Hero (2023) *Map of the Nairobi CBD and parking infrastructure*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.coursehero.com/file/p27j2ufl/25-Map-31-A-map-of-the-Nairobi-CBD-Source-County-Government-of-Nairobi-32> (Accessed: 3 February 2026).

Energy progress report 2019.

Guo, Y., Wang, J., Peeta, S. and Anastasopoulos, P.C., 2020. Personal and societal impacts of motorcycle ban policy on motorcyclists' home-to-work morning commute in China. *Travel behaviour and society*, 19, pp.137-150.

Kiley, F. (2026) *EMP-A transport sector modelling*. [PowerPoint slides]. Presentation delivered at EMP-A Training Workshop, University of Cape town, Cape Town, 26 February.

Kenya, R., 2019. Kenya population and housing census.

Kenya, R., 2020. Economic survey.

Ogot, M., Nyang'aya, J. and Muriuki, R., 2018. Characteristics of the in-service vehicle fleet in Kenya. *Draft report*, pp.32345-0.

Strategic Journals (2023) *Urban transport challenges: Vehicle volumes on Nairobi arterial routes*. [online]. Available at: <https://www.strategicjournals.com/index.php/journal/article/download/96/96> (Accessed: 3 February 2026).

Strathmore University Repository (2019) *Assessment of transport and traffic congestion in Nairobi*. [online]. Available at: <https://su-plus.strathmore.edu/handle/11071/5358> (Accessed: 3 February 2026). Report (FY 2020/2021). *Kenya Vision, 2030*.

Vision, K., 2022. 2030 Flagship Programmes and Projects Progress

